

voestalpine Metsec:

Building an AI-ready workforce
through employee upskilling and
responsible experimentation

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CASE STUDY

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Topic overview

This case study explores how steel manufacturer **voestalpine Metsec** (“Metsec”) – part of the global voestalpine group of technology companies – has approached AI adoption as a people-centred challenge, focusing on workforce upskilling, responsible experimentation, and employee-led innovation.

Developing capability before tools

Imagine designing a hotel from scratch. The process takes a long time: sketching layouts, refining the details, working through each section in turn, and checking that everything meets the required specifications. Now, imagine that once the first section is designed, an AI system recognises patterns in the structure and can automatically replicate equivalent sections elsewhere in the building. Some of the design work on the building that previously took nine weeks may now take only four.

For Thomas Baumgartner, Finance and Board Director at voestalpine Metsec since 2009, this thought experiment captures both the promise and the complexity of AI. More efficient design work could fundamentally change how a manufacturing business like Metsec serves its customers – but only if the organisation invests in training and develops a clear understanding of AI’s benefits and risks. “If we can design a building quicker than our competitors,” says Thomas, “the project can be built quicker and the whole supply chain benefits. I see AI as giving us a competitive advantage: if we don’t improve, our competitors will.”

Metsec is a UK-based company producing cold-formed steel sections for the UK building and construction industry. As part of the global voestalpine group, it operates within strict centralised data governance and IT and cybersecurity frameworks. Against this backdrop, Thomas has been leading an internal journey to explore AI not as a single tool or product, but as a capability that needs to be developed carefully and ethically across the organisation.

Participation in The Alan Turing Institute's Turing Way Practitioners Hub has reinforced the importance of responsible AI practices while offering space to reflect on what meaningful adoption looks like in a heavily regulated industrial context.

Real-world use cases through employee-led experimentation

Rather than starting with a mandate to deploy specific AI systems, Metsec's approach has focused on building a company-wide understanding of the technology. Central to this has been the idea that employees themselves are well-placed to identify where AI could genuinely help in their day-to-day work.

Through a series of internal workshops known as 'AI Test Labs', employees had the opportunity to explore what AI is, what it is not, and where it might be useful in their roles and departments. As part of the Test Labs, staff across the business were asked to suggest potential AI use cases. This resulted in 29 employee-generated ideas spanning themes including design, quality assurance, health and safety, compliance, maintenance, marketing, and customer experience. The example of accelerated hotel or building design mentioned earlier emerged directly from this bottom-up process, with AI seen as a potential assistant for Metsec's busy design engineers, handling repetitive, easily replicable tasks.

While some AI Test Lab ideas focused on speed and automation, others looked at reducing risk. One example discussed early on was the potential for AI to support compliance, helping the business stay up to date with changing legislation, technical specifications, and restrictions on materials, lubricants or any other substances required throughout the manufacturing process. In an environment where regulations evolve constantly, AI is seen as a useful way to support the decision-making of human specialists.

Importantly, none of these ideas were framed as finished solutions. They were exploratory, pointing to areas where AI could add value alongside the right training, resources and approval.

Balancing ethical considerations with practical elements

The AI Test Labs – which have now reached approximately 40% of Metsec’s workforce – form the practical centre of the company’s approach. Designed as three-hour, hands-on workshops, the sessions combine technical information with discussion of ethical, legal and environmental considerations.

Each Test Lab begins with fundamentals: what AI is, how it is used today, and the risks that come with it. Topics such as data privacy, hallucinations, deepfakes and responsible use are treated as a core part of the training, rather than an afterthought – part of Thomas’ ambition to ensure Metsec staff are protected in both their professional and personal lives from the risks associated with advances in AI. Participants are encouraged to ask questions and challenge assumptions, creating a space where scepticism is allowed and uncertainty can be discussed openly. To make the sessions more approachable and engaging, Thomas has introduced playful elements such as a showcase of creative AI outputs that even included a bespoke company song created specially for the Test Labs.

The second half of each session focuses on the practical application of AI. As Microsoft Copilot is currently the only AI package approved for work use within the voestalpine group, employees receive structured training on how to get the most out of the software they already have access to. This includes exercises using Copilot for tasks such as summarising emails, translating documents, creating images and infographics, working with spreadsheets, preparing presentations, and collaborating with other employees via Whiteboard or Loop.

At the same time, the Test Labs have broadened participants’ horizons beyond work. Using personal computers and non-company data, a wide range of other non-approved AI tools are demonstrated – from video generation platforms such as Synthesia to more functional tools such as transcription products. The aim is not to encourage unapproved use, but to help employees understand the wider AI landscape, what is possible through AI, and why rules, safeguards and approvals are important: a balance of curiosity and caution. As Thomas notes, it would be inconsistent to teach people about AI’s broad potential while suggesting that everything beyond a single company-approved tool is “black magic”.

Thomas observed a marked shift in engagement following the Test Labs: while only around 20% of participating employees reported using AI beforehand, this rose to approximately 80% in the weeks after attending a session. Moreover, 80% of attendees expressed an interest in receiving further AI training.

Implementing learnings from The Turing Way Practitioners Hub

Intern Tobias Leopold played a key role in translating the Test Lab concept into practice. During his time at Metsec, he helped design and deliver training materials, supported the Test Lab sessions, and participated actively in The Turing Way Practitioners Hub. The Metsec team was motivated to apply for the Practitioners Hub by the opportunity to gain further insights into AI implementation and how other companies are approaching the topic. Tobias says: “Through the Practitioners Hub, we connected with people such as startup founders and university researchers. It was incredibly helpful to gain exposure to AI perspectives and approaches from outside our own sector. All in all, it helped us confirm our way of thinking, fine-tune some use cases, and improve our AI Test Lab workshops.”

One Practitioners Hub session directly influenced a Metsec use case on data categorisation and preparation. The discussion highlighted how AI systems can help structure fragmented organisational data – an issue particularly relevant for Metsec and other voestalpine companies, where information often exists in multiple formats and is not always immediately suitable for use as part of a knowledge base. Application of these advanced techniques, says Tobias, could be a “game-changer” for companies across the group. Such cross-company interaction has already begun through the sharing of training materials, use cases and feedback, which will help others build on the same foundations rather than starting from scratch.

Challenges: Resources, approval and culture

Despite strong engagement and momentum among employees, Metsec’s AI adoption journey – in common with many organisations – has not been without obstacles. Because Metsec operates as part of a large international group of around 350 companies across the globe, decisions about AI tools and systems are subject to central approval. Issues of cyber security, data sovereignty and compliance with regulations such as the EU AI Act (including severe potential penalties for data breaches) are understandable and necessary at a central level, but mean that progress can be slow, even when use cases are compelling, and it is likely that other group companies could benefit from the same implementation.

At the time of writing, many of the identified use cases are awaiting additional resources and coordination at the group level. A central AI coordinator role at divisional headquarters in Austria – complemented by a similar but more operational role in the UK – would enhance the group’s ability to move from exploration to implementation.

There are also internal cultural challenges. Some managers worry about the time employees spend in training or experimentation – particularly when immediate project deadlines loom. Others are initially sceptical about AI. These concerns have come up repeatedly in discussions around AI adoption and can slow down progress even when organisational-level risks have been addressed.

“Just imagine you’re driving from London to Edinburgh,” says Thomas. “We were in the fast lane from London all the way to Birmingham – we overtook so many cars. Now we’re behind a lorry. We’re still on the way to Edinburgh; our AI journey is still continuing. But we’re no longer in the fast lane. As soon as we have the right resources in place in both Austria and the UK, we’ll move forward at pace again and this will be a real game-changer for the company.”

Next steps: Progressing use cases and exploring more advanced applications

Thomas describes Metsec as being in an early stage of AI adoption, where the focus is on how AI tools can assist employees in their roles, with training seen as a prerequisite for implementation. Looking ahead, Metsec’s short-term goals include restoration of dedicated AI staffing, progressing selected use cases, and continuing to expand training offerings through the addition of prompt engineering courses and vendor-led Copilot sessions. All of the AI Test Lab documents and training materials have been shared with the group, and other voestalpine companies from across the world are looking to emulate the Test Lab format.

In the longer term, Thomas envisages more advanced applications, including AI-driven customer interaction and agent-based systems that streamline the early stages of client engagement. Across all of these possibilities, careful implementation remains important, including understanding how data is used, assessing risks, and ensuring employees are closely involved in the process.

Reflections on *The Turing Way* Practitioners Hub

“We took part in The Turing Way Practitioners Hub to sense-check what we were doing and to make sure we were approaching artificial intelligence in the right way. There is a lot of excitement around AI, but also a lot of things that can be missed if you don’t stop and think about ethics, data protection, sustainability and risk. The programme was very structured, which helped us reflect on those foundations and refine our approach rather than rushing into solutions. It also provided reassurance that the direction we were taking – focusing first on training and awareness – was the right one. And we really valued seeing how other organisations are approaching similar challenges and to share our own experiences as we continue our AI adoption journey.”

Thomas Baumgartner,
Finance and Board Director at voestalpine Metsec

Key takeaways

- AI adoption at Metsec has focused on people and skills before technology and tools.
- Employee-led use cases have brought to light opportunities grounded in real-life operational needs.
- Safe, structured experimentation can build confidence without undermining company policies.
- Responsible AI starts with training and shared awareness – not just approved tools.
- Adoption as part of a large, global organisation can bring challenges around governance, approval and shifting resources.
- External communities such as The Turing Way Practitioners Hub can provide both insight and reassurance on thoughtful approaches to AI adoption for companies at all scales.

Contributors and acknowledgements

This case study is published under *The Turing Way Practitioners* Hub 2025-26 Cohort – case study series. The Practitioners Hub is *The Turing Way* project that works with experts from partnering organisations to promote data science best practices. In 2025, The Turing Way team welcomed **Thomas Baumgartner** and **Tobias Leopold**, as Experts-in-Residence to discuss and share their implementation approaches to data science and AI, as well as build additional skills around best practices in responsible, ethical, and collaborative working. We thank them for leading the development of this case study.

The Turing Way Practitioner's Hub was supported by Innovate UK BridgeAI from 2023-2026. BridgeAI empowers UK businesses in high-growth sectors, driving productivity and economic growth through the adoption of Artificial Intelligence. The programme bridges the gap between developers and end-users, fostering user-driven AI technologies.

With a focus on ethics, transparency, and data privacy, BridgeAI aims to build trust and confidence in the development of AI solutions. Strengthening AI leadership, supporting workforces, and promoting responsible innovation, BridgeAI shapes a collaborative and AI-enabled future.

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The Turing Way Practitioners Hub's 2025-26 Cohort was co-delivered by **Arielle Bennett**, Senior Researcher – Open Source Practices and **Dr Ann Borda**, Senior Research Community Manager. **Stuart Gillespie** is the technical writer for this case study, and others in the series. **Léllé Demertzi** is the Research Project Manager. **Sofia Pires** is the Case Study Liaison for this case study.

The Turing Way Practitioners Hub, designed and launched in 2023 by Dr Malvika Sharan, aims to accelerate the adoption of best practices. Through a six-month cohort-based program, the Hub facilitates knowledge sharing, skill exchange, case study co-creation, and the adoption of open science practices. It also fosters a network of 'Experts in Residence' across partnering organisations.

For any comments, questions or collaboration with *The Turing Way*, please email: theturingway@gmail.com

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